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A STUDY ON CONSUMERS PERCEPTION TOWARDS ATM SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Automated Teller Machines enables banks to provide to their customers very competent and cost effective. Customer satisfaction is completely dependent upon the exposure of services provided by the banks and perception is based on accumulated past experience. There can be seen a societal shift towards the Automated Teller Machine sector because of many advantages from using Automated Teller Machine has made the society as a whole to accept the advent of Automated Teller Machine and use it in daily lives. The main objective of the study is to identify the consumers perception towards Automated Teller Machine (ATM) services. The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through google form

questionnaire with 302 sample respondents on the basis of convenient sampling method. The secondary data has collected through publications. The sample respondents to be used in this study are ATM card holders. In this study customers were selected on the basis of convenient sampling

Keywords: Customer Perception, Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Banking Services.

INTRODUCTION

The Automated Teller Machines sector is a complete success story; banks have been able to serve their customers 24*7 and outside their premises because of the advent of the Automated Teller Machines. There are many

more factors that influence consumers to use Automated Teller Machines banking i.e. location of the ATM, speed service and grievances response. Automated Teller Machines enables banks to provide to their customers very competent and cost effective. Customer satisfaction is completely dependent upon the exposure of services provided by the banks and perception is based on accumulated past experience. There can be seen a societal shift towards the Automated Teller Machine sector because of many advantages from using Automated Teller Machine has made the society as a whole to accept the advent of Automated Teller Machine and use it in daily lives. The bank customers can withdraw cash from Automated Teller Machines and also make cashless payments through electronic transactions. Compared to Automated Teller Machines, online banking is even more convenient and has become a dominant mode of transactions in developed countries where most purchases are made online.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

T. Sathia Bhama and G. Sweetlin Subi (2022) in their study “A Study on Customer Satisfaction Towards ATM Services” analyzed the factors leading to the adoption of ATM services and problems in the usage of ATMs. The author found that there is a significant association in Satisfaction level regarding various factors of ATM services provided by the banks. The authors suggested that banks need to conduct awareness programs on the usage of ATM services and provide safety measures to their customers. The study concluded that bankers take necessary steps to take remedial measures to promote satisfaction to the customers about the usage of new technologies.

Chhemanand Joshi (2019) in this study “Impact of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction in the Nepalese Commercial Banks” analyzed the

relationship between dimensions of ATM service quality and customer satisfaction. This study was conducted in Dgandadhi sub-metropolitan city of Nepal and sample population of this study is all ATM users of four commercial banks. The author found that ATM service quality shows positive impact on the customers satisfaction, some variables have very high customer satisfaction whereas some variables have the lower customer satisfaction. The author suggested that banks need to pay more attention on their customer satisfaction.

Naeem Akhtar, Ali Raza & Others (2016) in their study “Impact of A.T.M Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction: An Empirical Study in Kasur Pakistan Banking Sector” determined the relationship between service quality and security with satisfaction of customers and also describe the future suggestions to managers of the bank to improve the quality of ATMs services in Pakistani banking system. The authors suggested that bank management should provide better service to the customers and work on reliability because reliability of customers in banking sector is necessary. The study concluded that management of banking sector should work more in pricing strategies because if a customer satisfied due to prices his attitude towards purchasing is positive.

Bashir Idris (2014) in this study “Customer Satisfaction of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) Based on Service Quality” analyzed the service quality of the ATMs services in Zamfara state. In this study author was collected data from customers in major banks of Nigeria. The study concluded that monitor the security operations at the ATMs centers and also create more awareness on how to ensure self-security to customers i.e. to stop responding to unnecessary emails, text messages and sharing pin with others. The authors suggested that banks should deploy the use of ATMs that are friendly oriented, that are made easier to use.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To identify the consumers perception towards Automatic Teller Machines (ATM) services.

METHODOLOGY

This study is mainly focused on to identify the consumers perception towards ATM services. The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources. The primary data was collected through google form questionnaire with 302 sample respondents on the basis of convenient sampling method. The secondary data has collected through publications. The sample respondents to be used in this study are ATM card holders. In this study customers were selected on the basis of convenient sampling.

SOCIO ECONOMIC PROFILE OF THE ATM USERS

The socio-economic profile of the sample respondents taken from both rural and urban areas. The respondents profile i.e. location, gender, age, education, family monthly income, mode of income are analyzed based on the primary data. The respondents profile shows in the following figures.

Socio-economic Profile of the ATM Users (Sample Respondents)

Figure-1

Address / Living Area (Domicile)
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-2

Gender
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-3

Age (Years)
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-4

Educational Status
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-5

Family Income Per Month (Rs.)
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-6

Mode of family Income Received:
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure -7

How frequently do you use ATM card ?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-8

Mostly What are the services availed and purpose for using ATM Card?
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

The overall analysis inferred from the above figures is that majority of the sample respondents are living in rural areas and remaining of respondents are living in urban areas. The overall result shows that male respondents are more than the female sample respondents in the study area. It is understood from the analysis of the above figures among the total majority of the sample respondents are graduates and remaining of respondents are below graduation qualification. The overall analysis inferred from the above figures is that the major portion of the respondents fall in the income group below Rs.10,000.

It is understood from the analysis of the above figures among the total majority sample respondents are rarely used ATM services, some of the respondents are used monthly and only few sample respondents are regularly used ATM services. It is observed from the above figure majority respondents used ATM Cards for cash withdrawal and online payment purpose and only few respondents are used for cash deposits, money transfers and card swiping purpose.

Figure-9

How long you have been using the ATM
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure -10

Mostly Which factor influenced you to prefer the ATM
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

Figure-11

Perception of customers regarding the ATM Charges
302 responses

Source: Primary data.

It is understood from the analysis of the above figures among the total most of the sample respondents are used ATM services from one year to two years. It is observed from the above analysis majority sample respondents are influenced due to easy to withdrawal money and 24*7 Services availability to prefer the ATM services. The above analysis exhibits that majority sample respondents are satisfied and moderately satisfied with the ATM charges and

some of the respondents are dissatisfied with the charges.

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Majority sample respondents are rarely used ATM services, some of the respondents are used monthly and only few sample respondents are regularly used ATM services.
2. Most of the respondents used ATM Cards for cash withdrawal and online payment purpose and only few respondents are used for cash deposits, money transfers and card swiping purpose.
3. Among the total most of the sample respondents are used ATM services from one year to two years. It is observed from the above analysis majority sample respondents are influenced due to easy to withdrawal money and 24*7 Services availability to prefer the ATM services.
4. Majority sample respondents are satisfied and moderately satisfied with the ATM charges and some of the respondents are dissatisfied with the charges.
5. All the banks need to create more awareness to their account holders regarding advantages of ATM card services.
6. The bankers need to reduce transaction charges and annual charges for satisfying the ATM users and also increase the number of Automatic Teller Machines at rural areas.

CONCLUSION

Majority sample respondents are influenced due to easy to withdrawal money and 24*7 Services availability to prefer the ATM services. Most of the sample respondents are satisfied and moderately satisfied with the ATM charges and

some of the respondents are dissatisfied with the charges. The study concludes that the banks need to create more awareness to their account holders regarding advantages of ATM card services. The bankers need to reduce transaction charges and annual charges for satisfying the ATM users and also increase the number of Automatic Teller Machines at rural areas.

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